

Interface elements - advantages and limitations in CFRP delamination modelling

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SUMMARY

Interface (cohesive) elements are well suited for composites delamination simulation. The commonly used bi-linear interface law is compared with an exponential law. Input parameters, mesh requirements and element order are discussed. The best performing interface law depends on the solver used while delamination predictions were identical.

Keywords: Cohesive law, delamination, finite element, interface element, process zone

INTRODUCTION

Laminated carbon epoxy composites offer great weight saving potentials over metals and are used extensively in the aerospace industry as well as other high performance applications. Laminated materials are ideal for shell-like structures due to high in-plane strength properties. The tradeoff is reduced out of plane properties where delamination is the main issue. Plasticity is limited to the microscale (in resin rich areas) and the global failure response is generally brittle. While through thickness reinforcement and tougher resins have been developed, cost and reduction in other properties still limit their full application. Delamination thus continues to be a problem and design engineers in the aerospace industry currently work to the 'no damage' criterion. Flaws are, however, present in most composite structures introduced during manufacture, assembly or while in service.

Finite Element (FE) based analysis is often used to assess whether a given flaw, or delamination, or component debonding, will grow and whether growth will be stable or unstable. Conventional stress analysis cannot be used as delaminations tend to have a sharp crack front and a converged solution is not obtained due to the stress singularity at the crack tip. Fracture energy based techniques are needed, the Virtual Crack Closure Technique (VCCT) being an example [1,2]. Here an actual crack in the mesh is closed by a virtual force and the Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR), denoted G , is calculated and can be compared against a critical value (G_C) which is a measurable material property. The seriousness of existing flaws can be ascertained with VCCT but the technique does not lend itself easily to progressive delamination simulation where multiple delaminations may interact and also an existing flaw is always required with VCCT.

Interface elements or cohesive elements are more recent than VCCT and are actual finite elements intended to represent a thin resin layer between ply interfaces or bond lines. When used for delamination modelling these elements can be inserted at all ply interfaces and 'virtual testing' can be performed allowing extensive multiple crack growth and interaction. One drawback is the requirement for a fine mesh, typically element sizes less

than 1mm are needed to give an accurate answer. In reality, to maintain feasible computing times, preliminary linear elastic stress analysis can point to relevant regions for selective interface element insertion. Work is ongoing to automate this task to reduce analyst workload and increase objectivity [3].

CONSTITUTIVE LAW

The constitutive law can be presented as a stress-separation law and the critical Strain Energy Release Rate (SERR) G_C is the area under the curve. Several laws have been considered by various investigators. Here we only compare two types as shown in Figure 1. The bi-linear law is the most commonly used and is available in commercial codes such as Simulia/Abaqus. Detailed descriptions of the bi-linear law have been provided by Turon et al. [4].

The exponential law was originally developed for the Imperial College in-house code FE77 [5] and has recently been coded as a user element for Abaqus Standard (implicit). The exponential law was introduced as an alternative to the bi-linear which has a negative stiffness and can cause numerical problems when unloading. Other exponential interface laws have been presented by investigators elsewhere, referring to an exponential damaged response. These should not be confused with the exponential non-linear elastic response used here which is of the form shown in Figure 1:

$$\sigma(u) = S_C \left(1 - e^{-\frac{uK_0}{S_C}} \right) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where u is the opening displacement, K_0 is the initial elastic stiffness and S_C is the strength parameter. A separate set of parameters are given for interface opening (mode I) and shear (mode II) and no interaction exists between the two modes before failure. The elastic exponential curves are truncated by G_C at failure when a power mode mixity criterion exceeds unity:

$$\left(\frac{G_I}{G_{IC}} \right)^\alpha + \left(\frac{G_{II}}{G_{IIC}} \right)^\alpha = 1 \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

The exponent α is typically set to a value between 1 and 2 but this is essentially a curvefit to experimental test data. A Benzeggagh-Kenane (B-K) type criterion is also commonly used [6]. Similar input parameters are required for both the bi-linear law and the exponential law: 1) Initial elastic stiffness K_0 . 2) Strength parameter S_C . 3) Critical SERR G_C . Damage is considered in the bi-linear law with gradual failure while the exponential law fails abruptly once G_C is reached (not unlike elasto-plastic laws used in ductile metals). Choice of input parameters and the omission of damage in the exponential law will be re-visited in the following text. First, results from a number of basic test cases will be presented.

Figure 1. Commonly used bilinear interface law (left) and exponential law (right).

Performance comparison of two interface laws

The performance of the exponential interface element was tested on three types of test which are commonly used to derive delamination toughness data. These are: Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) for pure mode I, End Load Split (ELS) for pure mode II and finally Mixed Mode Bending (MMB). Closed form theoretical solutions can be plotted for all three test types. DCB dimensions and material properties were taken from NAFEMS Delamination Benchmark 2 [7], repeated here in Table 1 which contains data for all three tests. The ELS model is similar apart from being shorter ($l=40\text{mm}$) and $G_{IIc}=700\text{J/m}^2$. Displacement is applied at a single point such that both arms will bend in the same direction and contact must be modelled at the interface between the two arms. The initial crack length was chosen such that $a_0/l = 0.5$. This causes crack propagation to be just unstable, followed by stable growth. For $a_0/l > 0.55$ propagation will be stable [8]. Mixed mode failure was validated on a test problem similar to the one presented by Mi et al [9]. The MMB test consists of a simply supported beam pre-cracked in the neutral plane at one end with contact modelled between the two beam halves. Load was introduced via a rigid lever, the length of which (43.72mm), was chosen to give a mode ratio of one ($G_I/G_{II}=1.0$). A linear mode interaction fracture criterion was used for this case.

2-d plane strain models were run in Abaqus/Standard (implicit) with 0.5mm CPE4I type elements (continuum, plane strain, four-noded, incompatible modes). Displacement controlled 'hard' loading is used in the tests, hence displacement was also applied incrementally in the FE models. Deformed plots are shown in Figure 2. Interface elements, marked 'x', were inserted at the anticipated delamination planes. Identical analyses were completed with the generic Abaqus bi-linear interface element and the exponential user element. Reaction force versus applied displacement curves are also shown in Figure 2. The exponential law captures the elastic-to-fracture transition in the MMB slightly better than the bi-linear law but the delamination predictions are otherwise identical.

It has been argued that the cohesive law shape matters under highly constrained conditions or brittle behaviour [10] and also shown to be the case with rigid substrates [11]. The latter may be somewhat extreme in relation to physical reality. The three problems modeled here all exhibit beam-like behaviour. It appears that the shape of the cohesive law does not influence results under these conditions.

One key difference between the bi-linear law and the exponential law is the lack of damage consideration in the latter. Again, we can say that in beam-like delamination problems under monotonic loading it does not make any difference. Should unloading occur, damaged stiffness can only be present in the small cohesive zone which will hardly affect the global stiffness in most structures. These findings may not hold eg. if the cohesive zone length becomes significant relative to the structure size.

Suitability for main solver types

Differences were, however, seen in terms of numerical performance. The bi-linear law has a negative tangent stiffness in the damaged stage, requiring artificial damping to obtain a solution. This damping needs tuning by the FE analyst where excessive damping affects the results, typically causing non-conservative delamination predictions. Too little damping causes slow convergence. The exponential interface law is positive definite until the point of abrupt failure. Artificial damping is thus not required and a converged

Figure 2. Force-displacement predictions with bi-linear interface and exponential interface superimposed on closed form solutions for DCB, ELS and MMB tests. Deformed meshes are also shown.

Table 1. Dimensions and mechanical properties used in delamination test models.

	DCB	ELS	MMB
Specimen length [mm]	100	40	100
Initial crack length [mm]	30	20	30
Width [mm]	30	30	1
Total height [mm]	3	3	3
Young's modulus [GPa]	126	126	135.3
Mode I/II strength [MPa]	56 / 56	56 / 56	56 / 56
Mode I/II fracture toughness [J/m ²]	281 / 700	281 / 700	4000 / 4000

solution can be obtained straight away without tuning. It should, however, be mentioned that the required number of load increments is approximately the same for the two interface laws once the optimum damping is used with the bi-linear law.

For a dynamic explicit solver, the bi-linear law is preferred. Here the negative stiffness does not pose a problem, in fact it is beneficial, while the sudden load drop in the exponential law causes unwanted noise.

MESH REQUIREMENTS

Cohesive zone length

It is well known that a fine mesh is generally necessary to obtain a converged delamination prediction with interface elements. Guidelines have previously been given in the literature to estimate the mesh size based on the cohesive zone length. For thin plates and slender beam-like behaviours the beam height influences the cohesive zone length as well as the material properties and pure mode expressions exist. An example for pure mode I is:

$$l_{CZ} = \left(\frac{G_c E'}{S_c^2} \right)^{1/4} h^{3/4} \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

where E' should be modified according to the degree of anisotropy. Cohesive zone length expressions such as Eq. 3 have been discussed by several authors, eg. Yang and Cox [12] and most recently compared with FE results by Harper and Hallett [13]. It was found that the analytically predicted cohesive zone length does provide a useful guideline but it is somewhat greater than that observed from numerical analysis with interface elements. This is in agreement with our experience. As an example, DCB data from Table 1 can be inserted into Eq. 3 giving a cohesive zone length of 2.5mm. Mode I stress versus crack tip distance plots were extracted from the FE model with bi-linear interface elements, see Figure 3. The converged result with a 0.1mm mesh suggests a cohesive zone length of 1.5mm. A 0.5mm mesh captures the stress distribution very well and the global force-displacement response is in agreement with the closed form solution for the DCB in Figure 4. Increasing the mesh size beyond 0.5mm has a detrimental effect on the force-displacement results. Looking at Figure 3, the 1mm mesh and 2mm mesh captures the cohesive zone within reason but the rapid variation in stress ahead of the cohesive zone is

not captured well at all. Stress gradients ahead of the cohesive zone are particularly high for DCB type specimens and stress becomes negative before returning to zero further ahead of the crack tip. The magnitude of negative stress depends on the beam height where a higher (stiffer) beam causes less negative stress which eventually vanishes when the DCB starts resembling a Single Edge Notch Tension (SENT) type test with a $1/\sqrt{x}$ stress distribution. This trend is illustrated in Figure 5 for the nominal 1.5mm DCB beam height (1h) and double height (2h). It is also seen that the cohesive zone length increases with beam height in accord with Eq. 3.

Figure 3. Mode I stress versus crack front distance in DCB with bi-linear interface element. Mesh size ranges from 0.1mm to 2.0mm.

Figure 4. Reaction force versus opening displacement in DCB. Mesh size ranges from 0.5mm to 2.0mm with generic Abaqus cohesive element.

Elements within cohesive zone

Several investigators have suggested that 2-3 elements are needed as a minimum within the cohesive zone [13,14] although more than 10 has also been suggested at some stage. From Figure 3 it appears that 3 elements within the cohesive zone are indeed necessary for the DCB delamination prediction. There is, however, no reason for this particular number of elements to be required to capture the stress gradient within the cohesive zone. The stress gradient is much greater immediately ahead of the cohesive zone and it is plausible that this actually sets the limit for mesh size. We are currently looking at quantifying this relation.

The displacement distribution ahead of the crack tip can be approximated by a beam on elastic foundation solution. This is of the form:

$$u(x) = Ce^{-\beta x} [\cos(\beta x) - \sin(\beta x)] \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

where x is the distance from the crack tip, β is a constant depending on material properties and model geometry and C is a constant depending on the applied load. The solution in terms of stress is superimposed on the FE results (where the cohesive law truncates stress within the cohesive zone) in Figure 5 using a low resin modulus of 1GPa only. While the agreement is excellent at this level, higher resin modulus values show discrepancies with the FE solution. Localised stress variation in the beams are ignored in the beam on elastic foundation solution, these are significant when the resin modulus approaches that of the beams. Work is ongoing to make use of the known stress distribution in enrichment of both interface elements and surrounding substrate elements at the crack tip [15]. To this end it should also be mentioned that other methods of crack propagation modelling are under continued development. Examples are meshless methods [16] which are related in some ways to the ‘informed’ FE enrichment and partition of unity also looks promising for many types of fracture problems [10].

Interface stiffness and stress gradients

It is often attractive to use interface elements with zero thickness due to ease of meshing or insertion in existing continuum meshes. Theoretically an infinite interface stiffness should then be used to avoid affecting the overall laminate compliance. This was accomplished by the perfectly plastic breakable bonds approach used by Cui and

Figure 5. Mode I stress distribution ahead of crack tip in DCB. Variation with beam height (left). Variation with interface modulus, and beam on elastic foundation (right).

Wisnom [17] although this suffered from other issues. FE based interface elements need a finite initial stiffness and a compromise has to be found where the highest possible stiffness from a numerical point of view is used [14]. Interface stiffness affects both cohesive zone length and the stress gradient ahead of this, see Figure 5. Yet, the interface stiffness does not appear explicitly in most (if any) mesh requirement considerations except for the beam on elastic foundation. This may to some degree explain the inconsistencies found in the required number of interface elements with the cohesive zone when looking at different delamination problems [13] and the variation in recommended numbers.

We now prefer to use interface elements with finite thickness wherever possible. Laminates are typically modelled with continuum shells representing plies and interface elements representing resin-rich layers between plies. A resin-rich layer of 0.01mm thickness with $E=5\text{GPa}$ results in an interface stiffness of $5 \times 10^4 \text{ N/mm}^3$ as an example of typical values. This value falls well within the numerically acceptable stiffness values found by Turon et al [14]. Using a realistic finite thickness interface avoids numerical issues in implicit solvers but also enables usage with dynamic explicit solvers.

Higher order elements

The exponential interface law was coded both for linear 1st order elements and for 2nd order elements. The generic bi-linear Abaqus interface element is 1st order and switching to the exponential law had no effect on the large errors seen in DCB delamination predictions with mesh sizes above 0.5mm (Figure 4). A fully integrated 2nd order element has three Gauss points along each direction. Multiples of these were tried in the interface element and it was found that optimum performance was reached with nine Gauss points. Results obtained with nine Gauss points in higher order elements are shown in Figure 6. Comparing like for like in terms of degrees of freedom, the 4mm 2nd order mesh should be compared with a 2mm 1st order mesh (in Figure 4). Doing so, reveals much better accuracy for the 2nd order element with a peak load of 125N versus 180N for 1st order

Figure 6. Reaction force versus opening displacement in DCB using 2nd order elements. Mesh size ranges from 1mm to 4mm with exponential interface law (user element).

(theoretical peak load is 100N). It is clear that results from the higher order element deteriorate less than linear elements for ‘too large’ mesh sizes. A fully converged answer does, however, still require the same number of degrees of freedom.

Interface strength

It has been argued that the strength S_C can be lowered artificially to lengthen the cohesive zone [14]. Larger elements can indeed be used but can also lead to incorrect failure predictions if the strength is lowered too much. A modified DCB with two pre-cracks will be used as an example since it highlights the interface strength issue and is generally a challenging test case for delamination modelling. Contact must be modelled and multiple crack fronts need simultaneous monitoring. The two-crack DCB was originally presented by Robinson et al [18] and has often since been used as a test case.

Specimen geometry and force-displacement response is shown in Figure 7. Initially, a conventional single DCB response is seen, followed by a sudden force drop as the main pre-crack grows unstably when interacting with the secondary pre-crack. This is followed by stable main crack growth above the secondary pre-crack, and finally both cracks grow simultaneously in a staggered manner. This was all captured well by both the generic Abaqus bi-linear law and the exponential law which provided identical predictions. The predicted force is slightly high in the final stage for the 0.5mm mesh used. Finer meshes did not alter this error. However, using too low an interface strength results in unstable

Figure 7. Two-crack DCB geometry and response for 0.5mm mesh size.

propagation of one crack, followed by an incorrect single crack behaviour in the final stage as shown in Figure 7. Exact material properties are given in [18] and are roughly similar to those given here in Table 1 for the DCB. Strength properties were, however, not given since VCE based FEA was performed by Robinson et al. We tried the Abaqus contact based VCCT implementation which gave exactly the same answer as interface elements with realistic strength. The two-crack DCB can be analysed without strength consideration but if a cohesive law is used then it must be physically realistic. Hence we believe that realistic interface strength should generally be used and that this constitutes a value similar to resin strength for meso-scale delamination modelling.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

A fine mesh is needed due to high stress gradients ahead of cohesive zone rather than due to the cohesive zone length itself. Further quantification is needed and this is in progress. Accuracy deteriorates less for coarser meshes with second order elements than with first order elements. With implicit FE solvers the positive definite exponential interface law seems better suited than the more frequently used bi-linear law. Dynamic explicit solvers cope better with the bi-linear law due to the gradual stress reset at failure. For the common delamination benchmarks tested here both laws give identical predictions. Physically realistic stiffness and strength values should generally be used to avoid spurious delamination predictions.

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